

EFFECT OF MODIFIED ZEOLITE CATALYSTS ON YIELD AND SELECTIVITY OF ETHYLBENZENE

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Abstract

Catalytic properties of ZSM-5 zeolite-based catalysts modified with cerium, magnesium, and yttrium were studied in a flow-through installation at atmospheric pressure in the temperature range of 350-500 °C. It is established that the nature of the modifier significantly affects the output and selectivity of the formation of ethylbenzene. Modification of HZSM-5 with modifiers reduces the yield of by-products and increases the yield and selectivity for ethylbenzene. The maximum yield and selectivity for ethylbenzene is achieved on the catalyst 4% Ce-HZSM-5, which is 38.3% and 58.8%, respectively.

Keywords: Alkylation, benzene, ethanol, ethylbenzene, HZSM-5, modification, selectivity.

Introduction

Among the numerous processes of petrochemical synthesis, the production of ethylbenzene occupies one of the leading places. Currently, about 90% of ethylbenzene, the global production capacity of which is estimated at 50 million tons/year is used in the production of styrene [1,2]. In industry, ethylbenzene is mainly produced by liquid alkylation of benzene with ethylene. In the presence of catalysts Friedel-Crafts, as well as gas-phase alkylation in the presence of heterogeneous zeolite-containing catalysts [3-7]. In developed countries, catalysts based on high-silica zeolites of the ZSM-5 type [8-12] are widely used. Due to the increase in bioethanol resources obtained by fermentation from biomass, large studies aimed at developing a selective catalyst based on ZSM-5 type zeolite for the production of environmentally friendly ethylbenzene by alkylation of benzene with ethanol [13]. The purpose of this work was to study the effect of modification of ZSM-5 zeolite by magnesium, cerium and yttrium on its catalytic properties in the alkylation reaction of benzene with ethanol.

Experimental Part

To obtain the catalysts, there was used ZSM-5 zeolite with a silicate feed equal to 45, synthesized at the "Nizhny Novgorod Sorbents" (Russia). H-form of zeolite was prepared by ion exchange of zeolite in an aqueous solution of ammonium nitrate at 80 °C according to

the method described in [14]. Catalysts modified with 1.0-5.0 wt% magnesium, cerium and yttrium prepared by impregnating H-ZSM with 5 solutions of magnesium, cerium and yttrium nitrates at 80 °C for 4 hours. The modified zeolites were dried in air for 6 hours, then dried at a temperature of 110 °C for 4 hours and calcined at 350 °C and 500 °C for 2 hours, respectively. Catalytic experiments were carried out in a flow-type installation with a stationary layer of catalyst with a volume of 3.0 cm³ in a quartz reactor at atmospheric pressure in the temperature range of 300-500°C, a volumetric feed rate of 2 h⁻¹ and a molar ratio of benzene: ethanol = 2:1. The reaction products were analyzed by gas-liquid chromatography according to the methods described in [15]. The acid characteristics of the catalysts were determined using ammonia TPD methods.

Results and Discussion

Modification of HZSM 5 zeolite with metals has a significant effect on its activity and selectivity. From Table 1, it is clear that as a result of modifying the zeolite with Mg, Ce and Y there is an increase in both the selectivity of the process and the yield of ethylbenzene.

Table 1: Effect of modification on the catalytic properties of HZSM-5 zeolite in the alkylation reaction of benzene by bioethanol.

Conditions: T = 450 °C; V=1,02⁻¹; C₆H₆ : C₂H₅OH= 2:1

Catalyst	Yield EB %	Selectivity EB %
HZSM-5	30.1	47.8
4% Mg-HZSM-5	34.2	53.2
4% Y-HZSM-5	36.4	56.4
4% Ce-HZSM-5	38.3	58.8

Modification of HZSM-5 with modifiers in an amount of 4.0 wt% leads to an increase in the yield of ethylbenzene from 30.1 wt% to 38.3 wt% and selectivity from 47.8% to 58.8%. The highest yield of ethylbenzene (38.3 wt%) and selectivity for ethylbenzene (58.8%) is achieved on the catalysts modified with cerium. According to activity and selectivity, the catalysts are arranged in the following order:

Ce-HZSM-5 > Y-HZSM-5 > Mg-HZSM-5 > HZSM-5

Thus, the yield and selectivity of ethylbenzene formation is determined by the nature of the metal modification.

The figure shows the dependence of the yield and selectivity of ethylbenzene formation on the concentration of cerium in the zeolite.

Figure 1: Dependence of the yield and EB selectivity on the concentration of zeolite in the catalyst

From Figure 1 it is clear that unmodified HZSM-5 zeolite, compared to modified samples, has lower activity and selectivity in the process of benzene alkylation with ethanol. A noticeable increase in the yield and selectivity for ethylbenzene is observed at a content of 2.0 wt% modifier in the zeolite composition. The yield of ethylbenzene increases from 30.1 wt% to 33.1 wt%, and the selectivity for ethylbenzene

increases from 47.8% to 52.3%. The highest yield and selectivity for ethylbenzene is achieved on samples containing 4.0-5.0 wt% cerium. On these samples, the yield and selectivity for ethylbenzene is 38.3 -40.2 wt% and 58.8-60.7%. Figure 2 shows the dependence of the yield of ethylbenzene on the operating time of the unmodified and modified catalyst.

Figure 2: Yield of Ethylbenzene for two types of catalyst based on duration time

It can be seen that HZSM-5 works stably for only 30 minutes, after which its stability sharply decreases. After 60 minutes of operation of the HZSM-5 catalyst, the yield of ethylbenzene decreases from 31.8 wt% to 13.8 wt%, that is, approximately 2.3 times. Catalyst modified with cerium in an amount of 5.0 wt% for 60 minutes of operation practically retains its original activity. The yield of ethylbenzene decreases by only 1.5 wt%.

Obviously, the decrease in the activity of unmodified HZSM-5 zeolite during the alkylation of

benzene with bioethanol is due to the presence of strong Bronsted acid sites. On strong Bronsted acid sites localized in channels and on the surface of the zeolite, in addition to the target reaction, oligomerization and polymerization of unsaturated intermediates occurs, which leads to a decrease in activity and deactivation of unmodified HZSM-5 zeolite. Indeed, as can be seen from the figure, with increasing duration of catalyst operation, the coke content increases. When the operating time of the HZSM-5 catalyst increases to 60 minutes, the coke content increases to 9.2 wt%.

Figure 3: influence of catalyst operating time HZSM-5 and 5% Ce-HZSM-5 for coke content

Unlike HZSM-5 catalyst 5% Ce-HZSM-5 shows stable activity within 60 minutes, which is associated with a very low coke content (0.7 wt%) in the channels and on the surface of the zeolite. Stability of the modified catalyst 5% Ce-HZSM-5, coke formation is associated with a decrease in the concentration of strong Bronsted acid sites and an increase in the concentration of medium Bronsted acid sites as a result of modification.

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